

Analysis of Rural Roads in Developing Countries Using Principal Component Analysis and Simple Average Technique in the Development of a Road Safety Performance Index

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Abstract—Road safety performance index is a composite index which combines various indicators of road safety into single number. Development of a road safety performance index using appropriate safety performance indicators is essential to enhance road safety. However, a road safety performance index in developing countries has not been given as much priority as needed. The primary objective of this research is to develop a general Road Safety Performance Index (RSPI) for developing countries based on the facility as well as behavior of road user. The secondary objectives include finding the critical inputs in the RSPI and finding the better method of making the index. In this study, the RSPI is developed by selecting four main safety performance indicators i.e., protective system (seat belt, helmet etc.), road (road width, signalized intersections, number of lanes, speed limit), number of pedestrians, and number of vehicles. Data on these four safety performance indicators were collected using observation survey on a 20 km road section of the National Highway N-125 road Taxila, Pakistan. For the development of this composite index, two methods are used: a) Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and b) Equal Weighting (EW) method. PCA is used for extraction, weighting, and linear aggregation of indicators to obtain a single value. An individual index score was calculated for each road section by multiplication of weights and standardized values of each safety performance indicator. However, Simple Average technique was used for weighting and linear aggregation of indicators to develop a RSPI. The road sections are ranked according to RSPI scores using both methods. The two weighting methods are compared, and the PCA method is found to be much more reliable than the Simple Average Technique.

Keywords—Aggregation, index score, indicators, principal component analysis, weighting.

I. INTRODUCTION

A road safety performance index is a type of composite index which integrates various road safety factors and gives their output in a single value. It represents the level of road safety of a particular road section in an easy way in a road network. A composite index is a mathematical combination of a set of indicators that measure

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multidimensional concepts, but they have no common units of measurement [3]. Road safety performance index is a technique used for evaluating the current level of road safety and therefore can be used to rank and compare roads [4].

According to the World Health Organization, worldwide 1.35 million people are dying in road accidents every year and this case is worse in South Asian countries in which 20.7 per 100,000 population die each year [1]. In a developing country such as Pakistan, the total number of road accidents in 2009-2010 was 9,747 and increased to 11,121 in 2017-2018, resulting in 43,773 people killed and 100,578 injured [2]. It is clear from the above-mentioned figures that crash data show only one dimension of road accidents that is in terms of number of people killed and injured. However, a RSPI includes all the factors which lead to crash occurrence in a broader perspective. Hence, the development of a RSPI is essential to improve and make new policies for road safety. This technique of identifying road safety is commonly based on fatality rate per 10,000 population or fatality rate per city, province or country obtained from crash data. This parameter does not account for many probable conflicts and does not provide enough information about the leading causes of road crashes.

In this study, a RSPI is calculated using two methods: PCA as a weighting and extraction method and Simple Average technique which is based on EW by combining four safety performance indicators i.e., protective system, vehicles, pedestrian, and road. The RSPI approach explains the road safety problem in the form of an index number. This RSPI will be used to identify safer road sections on national highways.

RSPI is a technique used for evaluating the current level of road safety and therefore can be used to rank and compare roads [4]. Road safety is a multidimensional phenomenon which requires an extensive range of factors to be combined to develop a composite index [5]. The data were collected via an observational survey using Tally mark method [6] on the N-125 road which is national highway in Pakistan.

Road Safety Index is the reflection of road facilities as well as the behavior of road user. In this paper, four safety performance indicators are considered, i.e., protective system (seat belt, helmet etc.), road (road width, signalized intersections, number of lanes, speed limit), pedestrians (number of pedestrians and number of road crossing facilities), and vehicles (number of cars, number of motorcycles, number

of bicycles). To develop the RSPI, 11 sub-indicators are used as input for the road sections.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previously, research has been conducted to develop a road safety index using international datasets which include the following parameters i.e., percent of health expenditure as GDP, infrastructure network density, seat belt wearing rate, and percent of road users using alcohol and drugs during driving. Wegman et al. [7] conducted a comparative study of road safety among SUN countries (Sweden, United Kingdom and Netherland) to develop an index. The main purpose of this study was to find national road safety policies and diverse ways to achieve road safety levels of these countries. It was concluded in the study how to develop a comprehensive benchmarking of countries-based on road safety performance and developments.

Al Haji [8] suggested a composite index and termed it as a road safety development index (RSDI). The data were collected from the World Bank, United Nations Organization, World Health Organization, and International Road Federation. Eight different parameters related to roads were integrated to constitute the RSDI. These factors were: traffic risk, personal risk, vehicle safety, road situation, road user behavior, socio economic index, road safety organizational index and enforcement index. The study proposed a methodology for a RSDI for comparing different countries based on road safety. It compares ASEAN countries and Sweden in the study. Hermans et al. [9] combined seven risk domains of road safety that were speed, protective system, visibility, vehicle, infrastructure/roads and trauma management. The data were collected for 18 European countries from international databases. The study proposed a new index and named it as road safety index (RSI). It concludes that selection of appropriate indicators and weighting method will reduce uncertainty in ranking of countries and will help to develop a robust RSI.

Hermans et al. [4] in another study developed a road performance index methodology based on five weighting methods that are Factor Analysis, Budget Allocation, Analytical Hierarchy Process, EW and Data Envelopment Analysis. The data were collected from the European Safety Net 2005 for 21 European countries on seven indicators. It ranked 21 European countries based on a RSPI using five weighting methods. It proposed data envelopment analysis which is basically a tool used for index development. Data envelopment analysis is the best as compared to the other four methods used in the research. Hermans et al. [10] worked on sensitivity and uncertainty analysis which is the last step in the construction of a composite index. It introduced a ranking of countries based on a RSI instead of road fatality ranking for 18 European nations. It also used two weighting methods: analytical hierarchy process and budget allocation. It is suggested that uncertainty and sensitivity analysis are essential steps for a composite index.

Wegman & Oppe [11] studied benchmarking for the road safety performance of countries. Benchmarking referred to the

process in which countries assessed several features of their performance in relation to other countries which are best in class. The basic indicator for benchmarking of countries proposed by the SUNflower-pyramid from road safety performance indicators that consists of social cost and number of people killed or injured. It suggests a benchmarking process in the field of road safety.

Gitelman et al. [12] developed a composite indicator for the benchmarking of 27 European countries. The work was conducted on the main layer of a road safety pyramid which consists of road safety policy performance, accident fatalities and injuries, and safety performance indicators. It was proposed that a composite road safety indicator is more realistic than the traditional method of road safety ranking.

Bastos et al. [13] worked on data envelopment analysis and cluster analysis for a composite indicator model. It used the data of 27 Brazilian states for the development of a composite index. It was suggested that a model based on data envelopment analysis was the most applicable in the field of road safety. Brijs et al. [14] studied international benchmarking of road safety. It introduces the theoretical background of the benchmarking process. A specific benchmark cycle was established for road safety which consists of five core activities. This study suggests theoretical and practical issues regarding the benchmarking process. Benchmarking does not show the result, but it is a continuous diagnostic tool which requires sufficient data, resources, effective strategies and successful implementation in order to improve the road safety situation of a country.

Reference [15] is on PCA for the construction of a road environment risk index. This study developed a Road Environment Risk Index which is a useful proactive method to identify a problematic road section as compared to reactive crash data analysis methodology. Tesic et al. [5] suggested a RSPI with limited number of indicators. RSPI with limited number of indicators is present in national and international databases. But high-quality and large number of comparable safety performance indicators is not present in every country and is difficult to be seen everywhere.

The literature shows that there are many factors on which RSI can be pivoted; however, it is required to identify the significance of these factors. The factors that are directly affecting road safety are more significant and therefore, this study selects the most critical factors compromising the road safety of road users. The methods chosen for the development of the index are simple and are compared to find the most suitable method.

III. METHODOLOGY

In the field of road safety, the development of a RSPI is still under explored. The research methodology selected is similar to that suggested by [9]. In the first phase, safety performance indicators (SPIs) are selected, and data are collected on the chosen road sections in the second phase. The third phase includes statistical analysis of the data and assigning weights using two methods to each indicator and the aggregation of indicators into the index. Finally, a RSPI score is obtained for

the road section. All road safety indices for individual sections are combined to get a single RSI for the entire road section considered in this study.

A. Selection of SPIs

The first phase of this research study is selection of SPIs. The selection was based on relevance, accessibility and robustness of the study problem as recommended by [16]. SPIs are described as the indicators that show the operational condition of a traffic system and which have an impact on safety performance [17]. The selection of indicators was based on previous research conducted worldwide [18]. SPI on which data were collected were divided into four categories.

Four major safety indicators i.e., protective system, vehicles, pedestrian and road were selected based on ease of data collection. These four indicators were further subdivided in to 11 sub-indicators as shown in Fig. 1.

a) SPI for Protective System

It consists of helmet wearing in the case of two-wheelers and seat belt wearing in the case of cars. In this study, the percentage of helmet wearing in motorcycles and percentage of seat belt wearing in cars are considered as SPIs of the protective system. Two-wheelers (motorcycles) are selected due to the enormous increase in the use of this transport mode in the country. In the previous decade, the number of registered two-wheeler vehicles has increased by 439% in Pakistan, according to a survey by [19]. The use of helmets can reduce deaths by up to 40% and injury by up to 70% [20]. People are using two wheelers as a convenient mode of transport because of lack of public transport in major parts of the country.

b) SPI for Vehicles

For vehicles, the sub indicators included the number of cars, number of motorcycles and number of bicycles. As the number of two wheelers is more as compared to other vehicles on the entire road network, they are included in the research to produce a well-grounded index.

c) SPI for Road

The SPI for road consists of speed limit on the road section, number of lanes, number of signalized and unsignalized intersections. For roads, dual carriage two-way highway was selected as most of the urban and rural roads in Pakistan are in this category.

d) SPI for Pedestrians

For pedestrians, the sub indicators include number of pedestrians and pedestrian crossing. Pedestrian is added as a new indicator as the pedestrians are the most vulnerable on the road. One of the major reasons for the consideration of pedestrians is that the majority of roads in Pakistan are dual carriage two-way highways in urban and rural areas with no facility for pedestrians.

Fig. 1 Schematics diagram of selected SPIs

B. Data Collection

The second phase of this study is data collection. An independent observational survey was conducted on N-125 Taxila Khanpur road that connects Taxila Tehsil, a subdivision of Rawalpindi District Punjab, Pakistan with the Haripur District of Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa province. Its location is 33°49'59.90" N 72°54'41.89" E [21]. The details of the road section are shown in Fig. 2. The road was divided into 1 km road sections and on each road section three stations were selected to get a reliable data. Data were collected manually using Tally marks methods which is a traditional method [6] in three peak hours of a day that are 7-8 a.m. at morning, 1-2 p.m. in afternoon and 4-5 p.m. in evening.

A sample of 60 hours data was collected throughout the selected locations along the road sections. The instruments used for the observational survey were an observation form, pen and a clipboard [22]. The selected road passes through residential areas, universities, villages, museum, hospitals and recreational areas. Traffic on the selected road consists of trucks, cars, wagons, bicycles and two-wheelers (motorcycles). Motorcycles, bicycles and pedestrians are more vulnerable to traffic flow on this road. Hence, this road was selected due to the high probability crash occurrence and it being a dual carriageway with no median.

C. Statistical Analysis of Data

The third phase is to analyze the collected data. The data collected for each SPI were in different units, as the data for protective system were in percentages, vehicles were in numbers and design speed limit recorded in km/hr. To make them comparable, the data were transformed into standardized values. Z-score method of the normalization of data was selected which is a common normalization method [23]. The formula for the z-score method is shown in (1) [16]:

$$I_{qc}^t = \frac{x_{qc}^t - x_{qc-\bar{c}}^t}{\sigma_{qc-\bar{c}}^t} \quad (1)$$

where I_{qc}^t shows standard score of indicators along a road section. x_{qc}^t shows individual or sub indicators scores whereas

$\sigma_{qc-\bar{c}}^t$ shows the standard deviation of indicators along a road section. $x_{qc-\bar{c}}^t$ shows the means of the indicators along a road section.

Fig. 2 Google Earth Map of the Research Area

Sampling adequacy is essential for the computation of a RSPI. To achieve this purpose, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity were performed. KMO is statistical test used to compare magnitudes of observed correlation coefficients to the magnitudes of partial correlation coefficients. The values of KMO test range from 0 to 1. Its values should be greater than 0.6 to perform with factor analysis [16]. Bartlett's test of sphericity is used for null hypothesis. It indicates uncorrelated indicators in a correlation matrix. It is highly sensitive to sample size [23].

D. Assigning Weights

Two methods are used to assign weight to the indicators used in the RSPI being developed in this research. These are detailed as follows:

a) Assigning Weight to Each Indicator Using PCA Method (Method-1)

PCA method [16] is used to assign weights. To perform PCA, the ratio should be a least 10:1; which means 10 cases for each variable according to the Rule of 10 which is basically a rule of thumb [24]. This method consists of four steps; the first step was to find a correlation between the indicators [16]. The second step is the identification of a certain number of latent factors with eigenvalues greater than 1. Factors which show a cumulative variance of more than 50% are used for further analysis. In the third step, rotation of

factors was done in which Varimax rotation method was used to minimize the number of sub indicators which have a high loading on the same factor [16]. The weights for each indicator were obtained from a component score coefficient matrix which is the last step of PCA.

b) Assigning Weights Using Simple Average Technique (Method-2)

It is a simple average technique similarly used by the UN and World Bank for the construction of the Human Development Index [25]. In this method all SPIs were standardized, then a simple average of all four SPI was taken. For the standardization of data, the z-score method was used using (1). Weights were assigned to each indicator, as in this case equal weights were given to each indicator. Equal Weighting (EW) does not mean no weighting, but it implies an implicit judgment on the weights being equal [23].

RSPI was obtained for each road section by summing up all the normalized values of four indicators and then dividing them by the total number of indicators which are four in this case. Simple average technique may be biased towards extremely high or low values in one or more indicators as it uses equal weights [25].

E. Aggregation of Indicators into Composite Index

The next phase for the construction of a RSPI is aggregation. Here, all indicators are combined into single

values. To achieve this, additive method is used for the linear aggregation of the SPIs. In this additive method, weights and normalized values of SPI were summed-up. The normalized values of the SPI were prepared previously in the third phase i.e., in the normalization of data see above statistical analysis of data. The formula for the composite index is shown in (2) [23]:

$$CI_{RS} = \sum SD_{RS} * W_i \quad (2)$$

where CI_{RS} shows the composite index along a road section; $\sum SD_{RS}$ shows the standardized values of the SPIs along a road section; and W_i shows the weights of each SPI.

F. RSPI Score

Two types of index scores were obtained using the PCA method and simple average technique.

Using the PCA method: RSPI score was calculated by multiplying weights (obtained from the component score coefficient matrix) with standardized data (z-score method).

Using simple average technique: RSPI score was obtained for each road section by summing up all the normalized values of four indicators and then dividing them by the total number of indicators which are four in this case.

The RSPI score for each road section was obtained and the road sections were ranked according to the RSPI score for both methods.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results show the developed RSPI from two weighing techniques and comparing both techniques. The results also show the critical factors that should be included in the study. Moreover, the better method between the two methods for a developing RSPI is shown.

Details of the results are explained under descriptive statistics of the data, sample adequacy test of data, communalities result of SPIs, cumulative variance of SPIs and

the ranking of road section according to the RSPI score by both PCA method and Simple Average Technique.

A. Descriptive Statistics

The results of Table I show the overall descriptive statistics of the data. The criteria for data analysis included mean, median, standard deviation, variance, skewness, and kurtosis. "N" in the table represents the duration of sample collection in hours.

For SPI (1) protective system, the mean of seat belt wearing rate is 17.85 out of 149.46 for the 20 km road section. This means only 11.94% people use seat belts on this road section. A standard deviation of 5.46 and variance of 29.84 shows not much variability in the protective system data. A high indicator value should always imply more or less causalities [5]. Similarly, the mean of helmet wearing rate is 22.29 out of 126.50. It indicates that 17.62% people are using helmets on the 20 km road section.

It may be noted that the data shown in Table I are highly skewed for pedestrian and road. For SPI (3) pedestrian it is between 1.470 and 2.984 and for SPI (4) road it is between 0.275 and 2.845. The kurtosis values for pedestrian and road are higher than 1 which shows the skewness of data.

Pedestrians are not using pedestrian crossing facility due to their unavailability; hence, all pedestrians are the crossing road from wherever they require. The values of pedestrian crossing and signalized intersection are low due to fewer facilities for pedestrians and also due to the dual carriage way with no median on the 20 km road section studied. Therefore, a lot of people cross the road and create safety hazard. Further, the number of lanes is approximately the same along the entire length of the road section studied and therefore the skewness is high. Moreover, the kurtosis and skewness values of pedestrian crossing and signalized intersection show high values due to low standard deviation and variance of data.

TABLE I
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS ON SPIs

	SPIs	N	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness (Pearson)	Kurtosis (Pearson)
SPI (1) Protective System	% Seat Belt Wearing Rate	60	17.85	18.57	5.46	29.84	0.381	-0.441
	% Helmet Wearing Rate	60	22.29	22.26	7.74	60.05	0.321	-0.386
SPI (2) Vehicles (cars, two-wheeler)	Number of Cars	60	149.46	140.0	41.67	1736.34	0.796	0.304
	Number of Motorcycles	60	126.50	130.3	33.45	1119.18	0.371	0.341
	Number of Bicycles	60	10.67	8.50	5.67	32.15	0.691	-0.507
SPI (3) Pedestrian	Number of Pedestrians	60	20.10	18.00	9.94	98.82	1.470	2.300
	Number of Pedestrian Crossing facility	60	0.62	1.00	0.38	0.149	2.984	8.686
SPI (4) Road	Number of Lanes	60	1.45	1.00	0.76	0.58	1.542	1.215
	Speed Limit	60	49.92	50.00	6.93	48.05	1.263	3.661
	Number of Signalized Intersections	60	0.66	1.00	0.75	0.156	2.845	7.673
	Number of Unsignalized Intersections	60	3.40	3.50	1.65	2.74	0.275	-0.333

B. KMO Test and Bartlett's Test

To evaluate the acceptability of the collected dataset for factor analysis, two tests were performed: KMO test and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The sample adequacy of the collected data set is checked using KMO and Bartlett's test, as

shown in Table II.

The result shown by KMO for the dataset is 0.758 which is adequate for factor analysis. Normally, the value of KMO is from 0 to 1. The acceptable range of KMO test is above 0.6 [26] to produce a good RSPI. The significance value of

Bartlett's test is 0.000 as shown in Table III which is useful for factor analysis [24].

TABLE II
RESULTS OF KMO AND BARTLETT'S TESTS^A

KMO Measure of Sampling	0.758
Approx. Chi-Square	432.029
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Df 66
	Sig. .000

*a Based on correlations

As the collected data were a sample size of N = 60 hours, therefore the value of KMO test is low in this research.

C. Principal Component Analysis

According to the Rule of 10, which is the rule of thumb for PCA/Factor Analysis, there are 60 cases for each indicator which is acceptable for analysis [24].

TABLE III
RESULT OF EXTRACTION USING PCA

SPIs	Initial	Extracted
SPI (1) Protective System	% Seat Belt Wearing Rate	1.000 0.658
	% Helmet Wearing Rate	1.000 0.455
SPI (2) Vehicles (cars, two-wheeler)	Number of Cars	1.000 0.603
	Number of Motorcycles	1.000 0.715
	Number of Bicycles	1.000 0.647
SPI (3) Pedestrian	Number of Pedestrians	1.000 0.508
	Number of Pedestrian Crossing	1.000 0.478
SPI (4) Road	Number of Lanes	1.000 0.650
	Speed Limit	1.000 0.596
	Number of Signalized Intersections	1.000 0.439
	Number of Unsignalized Intersections	1.000 0.645

Extraction Method: PCA

The data set sample N = 60 refers to 60 hours of data for each SPI collected on the road sections which is enough for the PCA. The next phase was to check the variance explained by each indicator. PCA was used as an extraction method, the first phase after applying PCA gave an output in the form of communalities tables.

The communalities result of the data is shown in Table III. The communalities result ranges from 0.439 to 0.715 of each indicator. All indicators show values greater than 0.300 which is suitable for further analysis [26].

The Rotated Component Matrix is the second output of PCA. In this phase, Varimax and Kaiser Normalization were used as a rotation method. Varimax Rotation minimizes the number of sub indicators that have a high loading on the same factors.

The results of the Rotated Component Matrix and total variance of each component for the four SPI extracted using the method of Varimax with Kaiser Normalization are shown in Table IV. The cumulative variance shown by SPI (1) Protective System is 25.909%, SPI (2) Vehicles is 16.352%, SPI (3) Pedestrian is 10.376% and SPI (4) Road is 9.705%. The four components extracted from PCA with eigenvalues greater than 1 show an overall total variance of 62.34% which is adequate to continue with the PCA analysis.

TABLE IV
RESULT OF ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX^A

SPIs		Components				% Variance
		1	2	3	4	
SPI (1) Protective System	% Seat Belt Wearing Rate	.752	-.303	-.207	.038	25.909%
	% Helmet Wearing Rate	.799	-.325	-.069	-.018	
SPI (2) Vehicles (cars, two-wheelers)	Number of Cars	.624	.055	.154	.189	16.352%
	Number of Motorcycles	-.018	.781	-.028	.277	
	Number of Bicycles	.054	.242	.721	-.164	
SPI (3) Pedestrian	Number of Pedestrians	.728	.138	.186	.064	10.376%
	Number of Pedestrian Crossing	.017	.036	.162	.787	
SPI (4) Road	Number of Lanes	-.147	.005	.407	-.659	9.075%
	Speed Limit	.317	-.549	-.045	.287	
	Number of Signalized Intersections	.067	-.228	.741	.147	
	Number of Unsignalized Intersections	.579	.537	-.005	-.175	

Extraction Method: PCA. 62.342%
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations

D. Weights and Aggregation

Using the PCA method: Weights were assigned to each SPI which were acquired from the component score coefficient matrix. Seat belt was assigned a weight of 0.291 and helmet wearing a weight of 0.443 as shown in Table V. These weights were linearly multiplied with standardized values of seat belt wearing rate and helmet wearing rate to obtain the RSPI score.

TABLE V
WEIGHTS ASSIGNED TO EACH INDICATOR (METHOD 1 PCA)

SPIs	Weights
SPI (1) Protective System	% Seat Belt Wearing 0.291
	% Helmet Wearing 0.443
SPI (2) Vehicles (cars, two-wheelers)	Number of Cars 0.297
	Number of Motorcycles 0.628
	Number of Bicycles 0.343
SPI (3) Pedestrian	Number of Pedestrians 0.436
	Number Pedestrians Crossing 0.116
SPI (4) Road	Number of Lanes 0.313
	Speed limit 0.378
	Number of Signalized Intersections 0.295
	Number of Unsignalized Intersections 0.155

Components Score Coefficient Matrix
Weights Assigned to each indicator using PCA

Aggregation of indicators was done using additive method by linear multiplication of weight with the standardized score of each indicator obtained from the z-score method to produce a RSPI. For example, the weight for seat belt 0.291 (Table V) and its standardized value -2.55691 are multiplied using (2).

$$\text{Composite Index} = \text{Weights} * \sum \text{Standard values}$$

$$CI = 0.291 * -2.55691 = -0.7440$$

which becomes the individual index. All individual indices for a road section are linearly added to form the RSPI for one section. Similarly, each weight was summed up and then

multiplied along the 20 road sections vertically, then they are summed up horizontally along each indicator as given in (2). The weights of each SPI were obtained from the Components Score Coefficient Matrix given in Table V.

Using EW: The weights in this method are assumed to be equal. The standardized data of all four SPIs are summed up then divided by the total number of indicators, which are four in this case. For example, the summation of all the standardized values of SPIs for Road Section 1 is 15.311 and the total number of sub indicators is 11. Therefore, it becomes $\sum SD = 15.311$ for Road section 1 and it is divided by 11 which is equal to 1.391. This value 1.391 is the RSPI score for Road section 1 as shown in Table V. In the same way, the RSPI value for Road section 2 using EW is 0.53.

E. RSPI Score and Ranking

The RSPI score is obtained based on four SPI (protective system, road, pedestrian, and vehicles) using two methods of weighting. All other 11 sub indicator weights were multiplied with their respective standardized values to obtain an index score. The road sections and their values in terms of the RSPI are shown in Table VI.

Road section 1 gets a value 5.94 using PCA method while its value is 1.39 using simple average technique which uses EW. This difference in values is because the PCA method and simple average technique used different approaches. In the PCA method, weights are assigned to each indicator through a scientific approach whereas in simple average technique, weights are assumed to be equal for each indicator. Simple average technique may be biased for one or more indicator whereas PCA method is more sensitive in assigning weights to each indicator.

TABLE VI
RESULT OF RSPI USING PCA METHOD AND EW

Road Section	RSPI using PCA	RSPI using EW	Road Section	RSPI using PCA	RSPI using EW
Section 1	5.94	1.39	Section 11	3.60	2.65
Section 2	-0.17	0.53	Section 12	-0.62	-1.41
Section 3	1.28	0.62	Section 13	3.87	0.75
Section 4	1.95	0.77	Section 14	3.39	0.47
Section 5	-1.62	0.56	Section 15	2.44	0.14
Section 6	-2.06	0.79	Section 16	-2.73	-1.12
Section 7	-2.82	-1.04	Section 17	-1.04	-0.31
Section 8	-1.53	-0.15	Section 18	-1.52	-0.96
Section 9	-0.91	0.56	Section 19	-2.89	-1.06
Section 10	-2.34	0.43	Section 20	-2.42	-1.20

The results of Fig. 3 show the ranking, road section and RSPI score. After plotting the RSPI against the ranking of road section, it was found that a high correlation is present between ranking and RSPI.

In Fig. 3, the RSPI is drawn on the y-axis while the ranking of the road section is drawn on the x-axis. Road section 1 shows the highest level index score of 5.94 while road section 19 shows a low value index score of -2.89. Similarly, road sections are ranked based on RSPI using simple average technique and EW method as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Results of Ranking, RSPI and Road Section using PCA Method

Fig. 4 Result of Ranking, RSPI and Road Section using Simple Average Technique Method

The RSI score is based on simple average technique and EW method; it may be biased towards one or more indicators. Using equal method of weighting, road section 11 scored 2.65 and ranked as 1st while road section 12 scored -1.41 and ranked as 20th. From this result, policymakers can focus on the safety situation of each road section in terms of its RSPI score and take the necessary steps to improve it.

V. CONCLUSION

RSPI is developing as a major policy subject in the world. It can be used for implementing various good safety practices on road sections. To increase road safety, development of a RSPI is essential in developing countries. Selection of indicators based on accessibility and availability is necessary to collect reliable data that can be used as a sample for city or country roads. The existing SPIs such as road, protective system, and vehicles were selected, and another indicator pedestrian was introduced as a new vulnerable indicator for road safety. The RSPI was developed for the national highway N-125 Taxila, Pakistan using the tally mark method for the collection of data. The main focus of this study was to develop a RSPI for a road

section in a developing country like Pakistan.

From the results it is concluded that:

- The input factors chosen for the study were significant to produce a good RSPI for road sections.
- The data used in this research have been found suitable for the factor analysis which adds in the integrity of the RSPI.
- The RSPI has been successfully developed in the study and the model has reflected the actual situation on the road.
- Using existing method of weighting, PCA and EW, it was found that PCA method was more reliable and suitable for composite index construction as compared to the simple average technique which uses EW.

The RSPI developed in this research is applicable to dual carriage way roads. The limitation of this RSPI is that it does not include three wheelers as a sub indicator as these vehicles are the major transport facilities used by people in developing countries.

In future research, data on SPIs such as trauma management, drugs and alcohol and speed should be collected to obtain a well-grounded composite index. Another crucial factor that should be included in RSPI development is the number of fatalities along each section of road. Fatalities per road section are essential for a reliable index, as currently this data type does not exist in developing countries.

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